

Stepchild in the Novel *Garis Luka* by Khairani Hasan: Dynamics of Powerlessness

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Abstract

This study examines the dynamics of powerlessness experienced by stepchildren in the novel *Garis Luka* by Khairani Hasan, focusing on the character Agra. The main issue explored is how psychological, social, and emotional pressures from family and the social environment influence powerlessness and the formation of a stepchild's self-identity. The objective of this research is to analyze the forms of powerlessness experienced by Agra, the coping strategies he employs, and their implications for his emotional and social development. The method used is literary text analysis with a psychological approach, where data is collected through relevant textual excerpts and analyzed thematically. The findings indicate that Agra faces powerlessness due to excessive family expectations, such as the demand to always excel academically and never fall behind his cousin, Sakha. Additionally, Agra experiences ridicule, betrayal, and negative stigma from his social environment. Despite these challenges, Agra demonstrates resilience through hard work, independence, and determination to prove his abilities. The implications of this study highlight the importance of creating a more empathetic and supportive family and social environment for stepchildren, as well as the need for psychological interventions and social support programs to help them cope with pressure and develop emotional resilience.

Keywords: *Love, social relationships, emotional resilience, Garis Luka novel, Khairani Hasan.*

Suggested citation: Purwaningtias, A. & Pamungkas, O.Y. (2025). Stepchild in the Novel *Garis Luka* by Khairani Hasan: Dynamics of Powerlessness. *European Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(2), 202-213. DOI: 10.59324/ejahss.2025.2(2).22

Introduction

Literary works are a form of creativity in language that contain a series of inner experiences and imagination derived from the author's contemplation. The object of literary works is human life, conveyed through language as its medium (Chriszia, 2020). The language in literary works, particularly novels, allows authors to explore various aspects of life in a deep, touching, and often thought-provoking manner (Hutasoit et al., 2023). As explained by (Sanjaya et al., 2022) Literary works are a reflection of the author's inner experiences regarding societal life, expressed in written form and possessing artistic value, making them enjoyable for all and serving as both entertainment and a source of learning for readers. The novel *Garis Luka* by Khairani Hasan tells the story of Agra, a handsome and popular teenager from a wealthy family who is burdened by his father's expectations regarding academic performance. In his quest for freedom, Agra takes advantage of Zeta, using her help with assignments and exams in exchange for a promise of a relationship. However, he never fulfills this promise, and Zeta eventually realizes that her feelings are unappreciated. As their relationship deteriorates, Agra becomes even more distant from

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his father, further straining their bond. This novel highlights the importance of parental support in maintaining teenagers' mental health (Tulfauziah et al., 2024).

A nuclear family generally consists of a father, mother, and children. However, the phenomenon of children being raised by stepparents often occurs due to death or divorce. Unfortunately, society tends to perceive stepparents, especially stepmothers, negatively, portraying them as cruel and unjust figures. This stigma is reinforced by media representations, such as the film *Rataplan Anak Tiri* and folktales like *Bawang Putih dan Bawang Merah*. Such perceptions not only shape societal views but also influence the dynamics of relationships within stepfamilies (Sari et al., 2019). Interdisciplinary studies on the challenges faced by stepchildren have been conducted, yet a significant research gap remains, particularly in the representation of the novel *Garis Luka* by Khairani Hasan. First, existing literature has not comprehensively explored adolescents' adjustment to their stepfathers. Second, the interpersonal communication dynamics of stepchildren within new family structures have not been thoroughly examined. Third, studies on children's resilience in stepfamilies are still limited. Fourth, the role of socio-cultural factors in stepchildren's adjustment has not been fully understood (Edi, 2021). In-depth research using an interdisciplinary approach is necessary to bridge this gap and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the challenges faced by stepchildren in literature.

This study aims to analyze the dynamics of powerlessness experienced by the stepchild character in the novel *Garis Luka* by Khairani Hasan, an issue often overlooked in family and literary studies. The research focuses on examining the approaches used to cope with pressure and the resilience mechanisms employed by the stepchild in facing psychological and social challenges, as well as their impact on identity formation. Through a literary and psychological analysis approach, this study seeks to uncover how the stepchild character in the novel responds to challenges arising from stepfamily dynamics, including feelings of isolation, injustice, and internal conflict. The protagonist, who experiences life as a stepchild, is not merely portrayed as a victim but also as an individual who overcomes oppression through perseverance and affection (Angraini & Permana, 2019). Thus, the findings of this study are expected to raise public awareness of the complexities of stepchildren's lives and foster a more inclusive social environment that supports their holistic development.

Materials and Methods

This research is library-based. The object of study is a literary work, specifically a novel, making the research not bound to a specific location and conducted at home, in libraries, or other suitable places for compiling the study. This research employs a hermeneutic method, with data collection carried out through reading and analysis. According to Ratna (2021, p. 44) the hermeneutic approach is the most frequently used method in literary research. This approach is used to understand the meaning contained in the text in depth, especially with regard to the dynamics of helplessness of the stepdaughter character in the novel.

This study will produce a detailed discussion of the research object. Through intrinsic and extrinsic approaches, as well as an emphasis on humanitarian values, this study aims to reveal how the theme of powerlessness is represented through characterization, conflict, and social background in the literary work (Aminuddin, 2020, p. 24). The primary data source for this study is the novel *Garis Luka* by Khairani Hasan, published in 2023 by Black Swan Books. This novel was selected as the research object because it deeply explores the dynamics of stepchild life and the psychological and social challenges faced by the main character. Data collection is a fundamental step in research, aimed at obtaining the necessary information to achieve the research objectives (Priyono, 2017). In this study, the researcher employs the *simak catat* technique as the primary data collection method. This process involves repeatedly examining the novel and other relevant sources while taking notes on pertinent information. This technique enables the researcher to obtain quotations necessary for the analysis. The analytical technique used is hermeneutic analysis, which presents data through interpretation and detailed discussion (Ratna, 2021, p. 44).

In the analysis process, the first step is to identify the intrinsic elements in the novel *Garis Luka* by Khairani Hasan, including theme, characterization, plot, and setting, which help illustrate the dynamics of stepchild issues. The study begins with an intensive reading of the novel's text to identify relevant quotes, dialogues, and narrative descriptions (Hastuti et al., 2022). Next, the researcher classifies the forms of psychological and social pressures experienced by the main character through relevant excerpts from the text. The third step involves analyzing the coping strategies and resilience mechanisms employed by the character in facing powerlessness. The researcher then connects the analysis results with real-life social conditions and provides recommendations for the development of social support programs and psychological interventions that can assist stepchildren in overcoming similar challenges.

Results

Oppression

Oppression is a condition in which individuals or groups experience systematic suppression, pressure, or domination whether physically, psychologically, or socially that hinders their freedom and fundamental rights (Husni, 2020). This phenomenon often occurs in contexts of power inequality, where the more dominant party exploits their position to suppress or control the weaker party. Oppression can manifest in various forms, such as discrimination, marginalization, or exploitation, and is often reinforced by unjust social, cultural, or political structures. In literature, oppression is frequently depicted through characters who experience pressure from their environment or oppressive systems, as seen in novels that address social injustice issues (Nugraha, 2020).

In the novel *Garis Luka*, oppression is experienced by Agra. He faces oppression in various aspects, such as humiliation and being compared to others. The depiction of Agra's oppression is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Main Character Oppression Data

No	Category	Form	Influencing Factor	Quoted Data	Code
1	Family	Insult	Taking advantage of others to do schoolwork.	"What is your brain made of, Gra? You rely on others so much that you don't even use your own brain to think?"	O.01/GL.97
		Comparison	High parental expectations of Agra.	According to his father, there was nothing to be proud of about a child like him. Agra didn't mind, but everything became overwhelming when his father tried to make him like Sakha. Everything had to be better than Sakha, including his personality. Only at school could Agra be himself.	O.02/GL.125
		Physical Violence	Attempting to smoke nicotine.	Agra still vividly remembers being caught trying to smoke because someone reported him. Sultan stormed Leander's basecamp and beat Agra on the spot, leaving him completely helpless.	O.03/GL.135
		Physical Violence	Two subjects' grades dropped.	Agra felt pain in the same spot on his face. However, he didn't touch his cheek, even though it hurt. His father never held back when hitting him, as if using all his strength. His father was disappointed in having a child like him.	O.04/GL.148
		Comparison & Belittling	Comparing Agra to his cousin and looking down on him.	"You can't do everything on your own! You're not Sakha, who can do everything well! Whatever you try to do alone will never be as good as Sakha. If it were Sakha, Papa would believe he could do it because he's diligent, studies by himself, and always improves.	O.05/GL.159

				Unlike you, who always fails without my supervision!"	
		Physical Violence	Getting bad grades.	SLAP!!! Agra's body froze as a hard slap landed on his cheek. He had experienced his father's slaps many times before. He thought it wouldn't hurt anymore, but his skin wasn't numb yet—he still felt the same sting.	O.06/GL.175
		Belittling & Criticism	Agra wanted to study alone instead of with friends.	"You call that an overreaction? Since childhood, this kid has only brought shame. And now he feels so great that he refuses to study with Zeta, who is clearly kind enough to help him."	O.07/GL.189
		Physical Violence	Uncontrolled emotions due to his child's mistake, which was deemed embarrassing.	Sultan couldn't control his anger. He hit his son's head, pushed him, and Agra fell, scraping his elbow on the tiled floor.	O.08/GL.199
		Physical Violence	Agra made a mistake that damaged the family's reputation.	SLAP!!! "If you want to get hurt by making trouble out there, go ahead! If you want to die out there, go ahead! But don't create problems that embarrass me like this!"	O.09/GL.289
		Public Humiliation	Intentionally embarrassing Agra in front of others for his mistakes.	"Agra never thinks ahead, he just plays it safe," Putra added. Sakha's father laughed briefly before addressing Agra again. "Don't run away from home again, Gra. That's not good. It shames the family. Luckily, the news didn't reach our business partners. If it had, it wouldn't just be your father who was embarrassed—we all would be."	O.10/GL.350
		Manipulation	Sakha didn't want to look bad in the family's eyes, so he made Agra the scapegoat.	When they were kids, Sakha was the one who broke their grandmother's favorite vase. But no one blamed him—everyone accused Agra instead.	O.11/GL.370
		Insult	Desire to boost his own child's reputation.	Putra often exposed Agra's weaknesses. At every gathering, to ensure Sakha received praise, Putra always highlighted Agra's mistakes. This way, everyone believed that Sakha was the only worthy grandson of the Megantara family.	O.12/GL.384
2	Friends	Insult & Mockery	Agra was dating a "bad" girl.	"The kids from Tariksa, especially Vano and his gang, mocked you for dating that kind of girl."	O.13/GL.117
		Insult	Hatred and resentment.	"I want to make sure your grades drop. Congrats on getting yelled at by your dad," Zeta said before walking away. It wasn't surprising—Agra already understood how much Zeta hated him now.	O.14/GL.146
		Mockery	Jealousy and hatred toward Agra.	"Don't cause too much trouble. A kid like you with a lion for a dad should pray more often at home. Hope your life is always happy. But I prefer seeing you suffer."	O.15/GL.152
		Betrayal	Wanting Agra to be scolded by his father.	"You're really ungrateful. After snitching on Agra to his dad and switching his quiz sheet, you still dare to threaten me?" Sakha chuckled.	O.16/GL.202
3	Thugs	Physical Violence	Criminal plan out of revenge.	While running, Agra got trapped among a group of thugs who had been waiting for him.	O.17/GL.395

				Before he could react, he felt something hard hit his head, causing immense pain. He could do nothing as he was beaten like a thief caught by villagers. Then everything went dark.	
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Note: O = Oppression; GL = *Garis Luka*

Based on the data analysis in Table 1, the character Agra in the novel *Garis Luka* by Khairani Hasan experiences helplessness that predominantly originates from his family environment. His father, Sultan, frequently insults, compares, and physically abuses Agra, such as comparing him to his cousin, Sakha, and slapping or hitting him when he fails to meet academic expectations. This indicates that the psychological and physical pressure from his family damages Agra's self-esteem and limits his personal growth. Although Agra is an only child, this status does not guarantee happiness or protection from pressure, as explained by (Amalia et al., 2023) regarding the complexity of relationships in blended families. Furthermore, oppression in this novel is not only limited to the relationship between a stepchild and the family but also reflects a broader social reality (Kendari, 2025). However, the family remains the primary source of Agra's suffering, emphasizing that conflicts in blended families can significantly impact a child's psychological well-being.

These findings highlight the complexity of stepchildren's helplessness, particularly in an unsupportive family environment. Although Agra is an only child, the pressure-filled family environment makes him unhappy, reinforcing the notion that being an only child does not always guarantee happiness. This study provides insight into the importance of coping strategies and resilience mechanisms to help individuals in similar situations while emphasizing the need to create an inclusive and supportive family environment for stepchildren, as explained by (Mahmud, 2022).

Love

Love is a feeling that grows within the heart, where a person sincerely cares for and brings happiness to their loved ones. Love manifests in the form of sympathy and empathy toward the beloved naturally and without pretense (Supriyanto et al., 2023). Thus, love embodies the true essence of humanity. Genuine love is marked by a sincere willingness to give more than to receive and by setting aside personal interests to bring happiness to the loved one (Rahmatullah, 2021). The ability to love and care is an inherent trait in children. The character of loving and caring is universal and the same in all children. This means that every child possesses this trait. It is an innate and instinctive characteristic. However, whether this character develops positively or negatively depends on the discipline and learning from the people surrounding the child (Sakdiah, 2017).

In the novel *Garis Luka*, love is a central theme explored through various relationships, particularly the relationship between Agra and those around him. The depiction of love experienced by Agra is presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Main Character Love Data

No	Type	Form	Influencing Factor	Quoted Data	Code
1	Friend	Care	Concern for Agra's safety.	"Agra! That's dangerous, you could get hurt. Don't look for trouble with them!" the girl shouted again.	L.01/GL.6
		Attention	Agra's physical condition due to scratches.	Zeta smiled when Agra was finally in front of her. Seeing the scratch on Agra's face made her worried.	L.02/GL.7
		Sacrifice	Love for Agra.	Rezeta Ivana was the girl's full name. She liked what Agra liked. She avoided what Agra disliked. Because everything about Zeta was Agra.	L.03/GL.9
		Protection	Covering up Agra's mistakes so he wouldn't get scolded by his father.	Come to think of it, Zeta often protected him. She knew a lot about his actions but still covered for him.	L.04/GL.79

		Support	The desire to ease Agra's burden.	She made that dream repellent while hoping that Agra would stop feeling pressured by his father. And hopefully, Agra would always be happy.	L.05/GL.141
2	Family	Financial Support	Favorite grandchild and strong financial background.	Agra and Sakha were the grandfather's two favorite grandchildren. If they wanted a car or a motorcycle, they just had to ask. The next day, it would be at their house.	L.06/GL.33
		Protection	Genuine love and a mother's protective instinct.	Even though she liked to nag, Agra knew his mother cared a lot. One time when he came home late, around one in the morning, his strict father immediately kicked him out. But his mother secretly opened the door, let him in, and that night, she became the shield against his father's anger.	L.07/GL.51
		Defense	A mother's understanding of her child's capacity.	"Papa, don't be too harsh. Agra knows his responsibilities, he knows when he needs to study hard. His grades have always been satisfying for me, so there's no need to push him to get even better ones," said Fanya, defending her son.	L.08/GL.158
		Protection	Empathy toward her child.	But she was a mother, there was no way she would let her child get hurt, especially by his own father.	L.09/GL.192
		Support	Favorite grandchild.	A small chuckle was heard. "Alright, Grandpa will talk to your father. Don't worry about it too much. If Agra doesn't want to study abroad, then it won't happen."	L.10/GL.307
		Concern	The desire to protect her child's dignity.	Because she didn't want any questions from others that could hurt her son's feelings.	L.11/GL.351
		Defense	Not wanting her child to be insulted.	Sultan became even more furious because Putra still dared to argue. "He is my son, and this is my family's business. Why do you have so much to say? Do you think you can speak like that in front of me? Do I need to show you how many people I've destroyed for insulting my son?! Do you want to be one of them?!"	L.12/GL.379
		Protection	The desire to make Agra strong and independent.	Sultan wanted to shape Agra into someone strong and capable. Because if one day Agra had to live without the Megantara family name, he wanted his son to still stand tall.	L.13/GL.385
		Worry	Wanting his child to keep striving.	I did say he was useless, I often said Sakha was better than him. But honestly, he is better than Sakha. My son can do everything, he is amazing. But I can't say that, I'm afraid he won't work hard anymore.	L.14/GL.401
		Affection	Favorite grandchild and only child.	His grandfather truly loved him, not just out of pity. And it was true—his father had always loved him. A love that wasn't visible, one that Agra wouldn't have understood if he hadn't heard it for himself just now.	L.15/GL.402

Note: L = Love; GL = *Garis Luka*

In the novel *Garis Luka* by Khairani Hasan, the character Agra, despite experiencing helplessness due to family pressure, also receives significant support from his social environment and family. Support from friends, especially Zeta, manifests in the form of care and protection. Zeta often covers up Agra's mistakes from his father and provides emotional support, demonstrating that social support from friends can serve as a buffer against stress (Alfiati et al., 2019).

Family support, although not always consistent, also plays a crucial role. His father, Sultan, despite being strict, wants to shape Agra into a strong individual, while his mother, Fanya, often protects Agra from his father's pressure. Agra's grandfather provides both material and emotional support, creating a more supportive environment. Overall, the support Agra receives from friends and family underscores the importance of a supportive social environment in helping individuals cope with pressure and develop

resilience. These findings highlight the importance of creating a supportive environment, both within the family and social circles, to help individuals overcome life's challenges (Dami, 2018).

Struggle

Struggle is an effort undertaken to achieve a goal, carried out by overcoming various difficulties and requiring both physical and mental strength. According to Nizam (2019), it is the result of a person's efforts in navigating experiences, challenges, and problems in life. The value of struggle can serve as an illustration of how significant a person's efforts are in life. Human life cannot be separated from the struggles of the individuals themselves. The principles of life's struggles take the form of concrete actions. The term "struggle" also implies activity, meaning the effort to compete for and strive toward a goal using strength, thought, and strong determination even if it requires fighting or waging war. The principle of struggle is tangible, often depicted through actions taken to confront or change a particular condition. Struggle aligns with someone or something that we consider important (Ningsih et al., 2023).

In the novel *Garis Luka*, struggle is a crucial aspect of Agra's life journey, reflected in his efforts to withstand family pressure, his search for identity, and the dynamics of his relationships with others. In this regard, the depiction of Agra's struggles is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Main Character Struggle Data

No	Type	Form	Influencing Factor	Quotation Data	Code
1	Self	Effort	Love	Don't think Agra never tried to like Zeta. He did. As many requirements as Zeta set, that many times he tried.	S.01/GL.37
		Hard work	Awareness of the importance of good results.	That's why Agra always studied, even if only when there was a test. He had already received predicted questions from Zeta, but he still had to study them. So that during the test, he could still answer, even if the questions were different from Zeta's predictions.	S.02/GL.124
		Sacrifice	Pressure from his father.	As his father said earlier, he had to study harder. And that's what Agra was doing now. He canceled all his plans with friends. Agra used all his time solely to sharpen his mind.	S.03/GL.138
		Change	Awareness of facing graduation exams.	Since becoming a third-year student, Agra became a good kid. He never caused trouble at school. When it was time to study, he studied, and he was very focused. Different from when he was in the second year, often asking for permission to go to the toilet but ending up hanging out in the corner of the canteen.	S.04/GL.167
		Independence	Desire to prove his abilities.	Agra stopped in front of a two-door shop that had been turned into a workshop by its owner. It had been two days since Agra left home, and this was how he lived during those days. Becoming a seventeen-year-old independent teenager. He worked at the workshop to earn money. When he left home, he left all his credit cards behind. The only thing he brought was his beloved black motorcycle.	S.05/GL.318
		Determination	His father's high expectations.	"My dad always emphasizes that I have to be the best graduate. Get higher scores than others. In elementary and middle school, I always failed to achieve that. So now I am determined to reach that target. I will work hard to become the best graduate in our class."	S.06/GL.338
		Achievement	The result of Agra's hard work.	Agra, you didn't forget, right? Today is the graduation announcement. You made it, your score is the highest among all students. Your hard work wasn't in vain. Don't worry about what others think anymore. You know yourself best. You know that you are the best version of yourself.	S.07/GL.434

Note: S = Struggle; GL = *Garis Luka*

In the novel *Garis Luka* by Khairani Hasan, the character Agra demonstrates various independent efforts to cope with pressure, reflecting his resilience and self-reliance. These efforts include working hard in his studies, sacrificing time with friends to focus on learning, and adopting a positive attitude in facing exams. This transformation aligns with (Belinda & Savitri, 2021), who state that positive behavioral changes in adolescents are often driven by awareness of responsibility and external pressure. Agra also exhibits independence by working at a workshop and striving to become the best graduate, proving his abilities despite the pressure. Independence is crucial for resilience, as adolescent self-reliance develops through experiences in overcoming challenges. Overall, Agra's efforts reflect significant growth in resilience and independence. Independence is a fundamental need for students, enabling them to complete tasks, believe in their abilities, and not rely on others (Nasution T, 2018).

Responsibility

According to Sa'adah & Aziz (2018), responsibility can be understood as an obligation that must be fulfilled by an individual or group, related to their duties or roles in society or within a specific context. Responsibility encompasses moral and ethical aspects, where individuals are expected to act with full awareness, fulfill their obligations, and uphold the trust given to them (Syifa et al., 2022). In the context of education, for example, parents are responsible for properly educating their children, providing them with knowledge, values, and life skills necessary to face life's challenges. Responsibility, as a central theme in this novel, is not only related to an individual's responsibility toward themselves but also toward others (Nursipa et al., 2023).

In the novel *Garis Luka*, responsibility becomes both a burden and a lesson for Agra, reflected in his efforts to meet family expectations, face the consequences of his actions, and navigate his role in various relationships. The depiction of the responsibilities carried by Agra is presented in Table 4 below.

Table 4. Main Character Responsibility Data

No	Type	Form	Influencing Factor	Quoted Data	Code
1	Family	Demand	Grades must be good, excellent, and must not fail.	Sakha nodded in agreement. Because they are the grandchildren of the Megantara lineage. The only descendants from each family. They are required to study and study. Grades must not be lower than nine. After school, they must attend many tutoring sessions. At school, they must be active in at least one extracurricular activity, which is why he is active in the music club. Meanwhile, Agra chose to be active in basketball.	R.01/GL.37
		Demand	Must not lose to his cousin.	When there are many tests like now, Agra rarely gathers with Leander's kids. Even though he is mischievous and often causes trouble that makes his mother frustrated, Agra is still aware of his duty as the only descendant of Sultan Megantara. He must be the top student in class; his father never gives any leeway, even when his competitor is his own cousin.	R.02/GL.124
		Demand	His father's ambition for Agra to graduate with the best grades.	"From now on, I will monitor all your grades. From regular practice tests, daily quizzes, monthly evaluations, to semester exams. There is no time for playing around because I want you to graduate with the best grades."	R.05/GL.158
		Demand	The desire to be considered useful by his father.	Agra knows why he has become like this. Of course, it is to achieve his father's target. To become the useful child his father always talks about.	R.06/GL.217
		Obligation	Must always show academic results.	At this moment, Agra is in his father's office. The exams are over, which is why Agra is there right now. He is showing his test results.	R.03/GL.137

		Obedience	Descendants of Megantara must not complain.	Agra knows his fate. After being born as the child of Sultan Megantara, he has no reason to complain.	R.04/GL.148
		Command	Obligation to take care of his mother's friend's child.	"That means we won't be able to meet. So, Mom asks you not to cause trouble for the next few days. Behave well towards Zeta."	R.07/GL.226

Note: R = Responsibility; GL= *Garis Luka*

Based on Table 4, the character Agra in the novel *Garis Luka* by Khairani Hasan faces various demands and pressures from his family, especially his father, Sultan Megantara, who emphasizes academic achievement and obedience. Agra is required to consistently achieve high academic scores, not fall behind his cousin, Sakha, and always present good academic results. Excessive academic demands can lead to stress in adolescents. Competition with his cousin triggers internal conflicts and lowers self-confidence (Khalda & Ihsan, 2023).

In addition to academic demands, Agra is also required to be obedient due to his status as a descendant of the Megantara family and to take care of his mother's friend's child, Zeta. These demands reflect family values that emphasize obedience and responsibility but can also create feelings of pressure. According to Nugraha (2020), pressure to meet family expectations can become a serious obstacle in adolescent identity development. This situation makes it difficult for adolescents to express their true personalities and interests because they focus more on fulfilling family expectations. The combination of academic demands, social pressure, and high expectations creates a stressful environment for Agra, which can affect his emotional and mental well-being. If not managed properly, this pressure may lead to anxiety, prolonged stress, and even an identity crisis.

Discussion

The novel *Garis Luka* by Khairani Hasan offers a deep portrayal of the dynamics of powerlessness experienced by a stepchild, with the main character, Agra, representing both the internal and external conflicts faced by individuals in similar situations. This study aims to analyze Agra's powerlessness, including psychological, social, and emotional pressures, as well as the efforts he makes to overcome these challenges. Through literary and psychological analysis, this research will reveal how powerlessness influences identity formation and the coping strategies used by Agra.

As a stepchild, Agra faces immense pressure from his father, Sultan, who demands that he always excel academically and never fall behind his cousin, Sakha. These expectations create a heavy emotional burden for Agra, who feels pressured to meet his family's expectations while struggling against feelings of helplessness and low self-esteem. His father frequently compares Agra to Sakha and even resorts to physical violence when Agra fails to meet his expectations. This indicates that Agra's powerlessness does not only stem from academic pressure but also from an unhealthy family dynamic, where stepchildren are often positioned as individuals who must constantly prove themselves. Studies suggest that excessive parental demands can lead to stress and anxiety in adolescents, which aligns with Agra's experiences.

Beyond family pressure, Agra also faces powerlessness in his social environment. He is often mocked, humiliated, and betrayed by his friends, such as Zeta, who deliberately sabotages his academic performance to provoke his father's anger. Taunts and insults from his peers, like Vano and his gang, worsen Agra's feelings of isolation and low self-worth. His cousin, Sakha, also betrays him by making Agra the scapegoat for his own mistakes, further reinforcing this sense of powerlessness. This situation highlights that Agra's struggles are not limited to his family but also stem from an unsupportive social environment, exacerbating his psychological distress.

Despite these challenges, Agra makes efforts to resist his powerlessness through hard work, independence, and determination to prove his abilities. He strives to meet his father's academic

expectations, even at the cost of sacrificing leisure time and social interactions with his peers. Agra also takes a bold step by leaving home and working at a workshop to demonstrate his independence. These efforts reflect Agra's resilience, even as he continues to face pressure from his surroundings. According to Nasution T (2018), independence and adaptability are key factors in overcoming life's challenges and hardships, which align with Agra's attempts to combat powerlessness.

The dynamics of powerlessness that Agra experiences also influence the formation of his identity. As a stepchild, he often feels unappreciated and looked down upon by both his family and social environment. However, through his efforts, Agra proves that he can overcome challenges and achieve his full potential. His achievements not only serve as evidence of his dedication and perseverance but also demonstrate that he is capable of developing a strong sense of identity despite being in a high-pressure environment. Mauliddya & Rustam (2019) state that intrinsic motivation and support from the environment can help adolescents achieve optimal academic success, which aligns with Agra's experiences.

Figure 1. Mapping Agra's Powerlessness and Resilience

Figure 1 illustrates the psychological dynamics experienced by Agra in dealing with the pressures and challenges of her life. The diagram is divided into four interrelated sections, each representing an aspect of Agra's powerlessness and resilience. The first section, "Striving for academic excellence", shows how Agra uses education as a form of resilience in the face of family pressure. Her focus on academic achievement reflects an attempt to prove herself and defy expectations that may have burdened her. The second section, "Leaving home for independence", illustrates Agra's courage to take a big step in her life. Her decision to leave home signifies her determination to achieve freedom and break free from the shackles that hold her back (Nugraha, 2020).

Meanwhile, the other two sections in this diagram highlight aspects of Agra's powerlessness. The third section, "Emotional burden from father's expectations", shows the psychological impact of high expectations from the family, especially from the father figure. This reflects the inner conflict Agra feels in meeting the standards set for her. The fourth section, "Isolation from peer mockery", highlights how negative social experiences exacerbated her feelings of inferiority and isolation. Nizam (2019) this diagram clearly demonstrates the balance between helplessness and resilience that makes up Agra's character, and how she attempts to overcome the various emotional and social challenges she faces. peer mockery", highlights how negative social experiences exacerbate the negative social experiences.

Conclusion

Khairani Hasan's novel *Garis Luka* represents the Dynamics of Powerlessness. The novel illustrates that, the powerlessness experienced by the character Agra does not only stem from family and social pressure, but also from the absence of space to express himself freely. Agra, as a stepdaughter, is trapped in the unrealistic expectations of her father, Sultan, who demands her to always be the best without considering her personal abilities and desires. This shows that powerlessness does not only arise from external pressures, but also from an individual's inability to articulate their needs and emotions in an unsupportive environment. In addition, the negative stigma against stepchildren embedded in society exacerbated the situation, leaving Agra feeling isolated and having nowhere to lean on.

Based on these findings, this study suggests a more holistic approach to understanding and supporting stepchildren. First, it is crucial for families, especially parents, to create a more empathetic and supportive environment where stepchildren feel valued and heard. Parents should reduce excessive demands and focus more on the natural development of the child's potential. Second, society needs to increase awareness of the importance of eliminating negative stigma against stepchildren through education and social campaigns. Moreover, psychological interventions and social support programs, such as counseling and support groups, can serve as solutions to help stepchildren cope with pressure and develop resilience. By doing so, it is hoped that stepchildren like Agra can grow up in a more inclusive and supportive environment, enabling them to overcome powerlessness and reach their full potential.

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